

Reactivity of carboxylato cyclophane with hexafluorobenzene and Cu^{II}-2,2'-bipyridine[†]

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Abstract : *N,N',N'',N'''*-Tetrakis(3-carboxy-propionyl)-1,6,20,25-tetraaza[6.1.6.1]paracyclophane, H₄cp is allowed to react with hexafluorobenzene (hfb) and the binding of H₄cp with hfb in solution is monitored using spectroscopic techniques (absorption, emission and ¹H NMR). However, a reaction of H₄cp with Cu^{II}-2,2'-bipyridine provides a solid complex of composition [Cu(bpy)₂(cp)]_n·4(H₂O)·CH₃OH (bpy = 2,2'-bipyridine) which is characterized using spectroscopic (IR, Solid state UV-Vis, ESR), elemental analysis and single-crystal X-ray diffraction measurements. The complex provides a 3D supramolecular structure using non-covalent interaction. Its thermal and photoluminescence properties are also described.

Keywords : Cyclophane, hexafluorobenzene, binding property, copper(II) complex, X-ray crystallography, photoluminescence.

Introduction

The term cyclophane is designated to a class of synthetic macrocycle which incorporates phenylene groups as an integral part of the macrocyclic ring framework. Cyclophanes play a broad and prominent role in host-guest chemistry, supramolecular chemistry, and molecular recognition¹. Several attempts have been made by organic chemists to develop functionalized cyclophanes, capable of acting as artificial receptors², carriers³ and enzyme models⁴. Cyclophanes are versatile host compounds and there are copious examples of structures in which the guest is either entrapped in the cyclophane cavity or is sandwiched between host molecules in the crystal lattice. In this context, the presence of a well fitting host cavity that is complementary with regard to the size, the shape and the functionalities of the guest molecule is of particular importance⁵. Molecules containing larger cavities bearing several functional groups open the possibility of encapsulation of various guest molecules. However, among intermolecular interactions involving organic fluorine is of current research interest⁶. In this

context, it is worth to mention that gas phase interaction between anions and π -acidic arenes such as hexafluorobenzene are found to be interesting⁷. Keeping these precedence in view, *N,N',N'',N'''*-tetrakis(3-carboxy-propionyl)-1,6,20,25-tetraaza[6.1.6.1]paracyclophane bearing four carboxylic groups is targeted as a host for the guest like hexafluorobenzene; being electron deficient as well as prone to H-bonding.

Moreover, the expanding field of crystal engineering for the construction of one-(1D), two-(2D) and three-dimensional (3D) coordination architectures is of immense current interests owing to their structural and topological novelty along with their potential applications as functional materials⁸⁻¹⁴. Among them, metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) containing carboxylate ligands are extensively studied because of the varied coordination modes of carboxylate groups hence leading to the formation of different structures¹⁵⁻¹⁸. However, it is still a challenging task to develop successful synthetic strategies for the preparation of MOFs with intriguing structures and expected properties, as the assembly process can be affected

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by factors such as reaction temperature and medium, template, counter ion and so on¹⁹⁻²¹. In this context, a cyclophane bearing carboxylate groups, *N,N',N'',N'''*-tetrakis(3-carboxy-propionyl)-1,6,20,25-tetraaza[6.1.6.1]-paracyclophane, was chosen worthy of coordination with Cu^{II}-2,2'-bipyridine in view of interesting complexing properties of this ligand with diamagnetic ions like Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}²². The present ligand carries remarkable features as : (a) it contains four carboxylate groups, which can adopt different coordination modes in the formation of MOFs; (b) its carboxamide groups can serve as hydrogen acceptor and donor hence can facilitate the formation of hydrogen bonded networks and (c) the cyclophanes which can act as host in which the guest may be either entrapped in the cyclophane cavity or could be sandwiched between host molecules in the crystal lattice. On the other hand, auxiliary ligands, like 2,2'-bipyridine is known to impart the conformations of the flexible carboxylic ligand (*trans*- or *cis*-), and play an important role in the formation of the final structure of the complexes²³. Keeping these points in view, *N,N',N'',N'''*-tetrakis(3-carboxy-propionyl)-1,6,20,25-tetraaza[6.1.6.1]paracyclophane bearing four carboxylic groups is selected and complexed with Cu^{II} coordinated with 2,2'-bipyridyl rings.

Results and discussion

The appropriate acidity or basicity of the reactants for deprotonation of polycarboxylates is very important for preparing complexes, as is the case for some other metal polycarboxylate coordination polymers reported in our earlier studies²². Cyclophane H₄cp is synthesized using procedure reported earlier²⁴ and it was received as a gift sample from Professor Osamu Hayashida, Fukuoka, Japan.

In the IR spectrum of free ligand, peaks observed at 1739 and 1644 cm⁻¹ are assigned to $\nu_{as}(\text{COO}^-)$ and $\nu_s(\text{COO}^-)$ vibrations respectively. These peaks shift to 1650 and 1580 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex. Uncoordinated water molecules present in the complex appear at 3310 cm⁻¹. Due to poor solubility of the complex in common organic solvents, its UV-Vis spectrum is recorded in powder form and is shown in Fig. 1. The peaks are observed at λ_{max} 317, 446 and 694 nm from the complex. Peak observed at λ_{max} 694 nm in the spectrum of complex suggests a octahedral geometry around Cu^{II} ion in view of earlier report²⁵.

Structural description of the complex :

Selected bond lengths and bond angles with their estimated standard deviations are presented in Table 1 while selected parameters for weak interactions are listed in Table 2. The carboxylate groups of H₄cp coordinate in

Fig. 1. UV-Vis spectrum of Cu^{II} complex in solid state.

Table 1. Selected bond lengths (Å) and bond angles (°) for Cu^{II} complex

Cu(1)-O(2)	2.068(3)	O(17)-Cu(1)-O(2)	86.04(14)	O(5)-Cu(2)-O(13)	93.53(13)
Cu(1)-O(17)	2.022(3)	O(17)-Cu(1)-O(14)	96.19(14)	O(1)-Cu(2)-O(13)	96.04(13)
Cu(1)-O(13)	2.230(3)	O(2)-Cu(1)-O(14)	152.78(14)	O(5)-Cu(2)-N(5)	157.92(14)
Cu(1)-O(14)	2.210(3)	N(8)-Cu(1)-N(7)	76.30(15)	O(1)-Cu(2)-N(5)	98.26(14)
Cu(1)-N(7)	2.138(4)	N(8)-Cu(1)-O(14)	93.80(14)	O(13)-Cu(2)-N(5)	91.61(13)
Cu(2)-O(5)	2.021(3)	N(7)-Cu(1)-O(14)	85.56(14)	O(5)-Cu(2)-N(6)	92.00(14)
Cu(2)-O(1)	2.024(3)	O(17)-Cu(1)-O(13)	98.77(13)	O(1)-Cu(2)-N(6)	101.47(14)
Cu(2)-O(13)	2.094(3)	O(2)-Cu(1)-O(13)	94.24(13)	O(13)-Cu(2)-N(6)	160.02(14)
Cu(2)-O(6)	2.546(3)	N(8)-Cu(1)-O(13)	90.41(14)	N(5)-Cu(2)-N(6)	76.51(14)
Cu(2)-N(5)	2.124(4)	N(7)-Cu(1)-O(13)	141.06(13)	O(17)-Cu(1)-N(7)	99.80(14)
O(1)-C(1)	1.243(4)	O(5)-Cu(2)-O(1)	102.53(13)	O(2)-Cu(1)-N(8)	87.22(15)

Table 2. Selected parameters for weak interactions in complex

D-H...A code	D-H (Å)	H...A (Å)	D...A (Å)	DHA (°)	Symmetry
C(8)-H(8A)...O(4)	0.97	2.42	2.764(7)	100	-
C(58)-H(58B)...O(16)	0.97	2.39	2.725(8)	100	-
C(60)-H(60B)...O(18)	0.97	2.44	2.851(8)	105	1-x, -y, 1-z
C(101)-H(101)...O(17)	0.93	2.59	3.1296	117	-
C(101)-H(101)...O(17)	0.93	2.50	3.343(6)	150	-
C(102)-H(102)...O(16)	0.93	2.47	3.357(7)	160	-
C(104)-H(104)...O(6)	0.93	2.41	3.287(6)	158	1 + x, -y, 2-z
C(107)-H(107)...O(6)	0.93	2.43	3.328(7)	162	1 + x, -y, 2-z
C(108)-H(108)...O(15)	0.93	2.42	3.345(6)	172	1 + x, -y, 2-z
C(111)-H(111)...O(5)	0.93	2.50	3.348(6)	152	-
C(112)-H(112)...O(4)	0.93	2.39	3.211(7)	148	-
C(114)-H(114)...O(18)	0.93	2.35	3.065(8)	134	-x, 1-y, 1-z
C(118)-H(118)...O(3)	0.93	2.40	3.314(7)	169	-x, 1-y, 1-z
C(120)-H(120)...O(18)	0.93	2.57	3.015(8)	110	-

different modes in the complex as depicted in Fig. 2. In this complex, carboxylate groups coordinate as monodentate (A), chelating/bridging bidentate mode (B), chelating bidentate mode (C) and also bidentate mode (D).

Fig. 2. Two different coordination modes of H₄cp in the complex : (i and ii), coordination mode of deprotonated carboxylic groups (cp) : monodentate mode (A) chelating/bridging bidentate mode (B); in mode (ii) chelating bidentate mode (C) and bidentate (D).

Molecular structure of the Cu^{II} complex with atom numbering scheme is shown in Fig. 3. It crystallizes in triclinic crystal system with centrosymmetric space group P-1. The fundamental building block contains two Cu^{II} ions, four crystallographically equivalent deprotonated cyclophane (cp) and two coordinated bpy ligands. The metal (Cu1) center is coordinated by two nitrogen atoms (N7 and N8) from coordinated bpy ligand and four oxygen atoms (O13, O14, O17 and O2) from three different cyclophane molecules in a distorted octahedral geometry. Similarly, Cu2 center also possesses distorted octahedral geometry consisting of two nitrogen atoms (N5 and N6) from bpy ligand and four oxygen atoms (O1, O5, O6 and O13) from carboxylate group of three cyclophanes. Two Cu^{II} centers (Cu1 and Cu2) are bridged via two carboxylate groups : one in mode B and other in mode D (Fig. 2). All secondary building units are further linked with each other through carboxylate groups of cp ligand to form a 3D network as shown in Fig. 4. Thus, the ligand H₄cp, possesses two different coordination modes (i) and (ii) (Fig. 2). In mode (i) two carboxylates groups act in unidentate mode (A) and two carboxylates act in chelating/bridging bidentate mode (B) whereas in mode (ii) two carboxylate groups act in chelating bidentate mode (C) and remaining two carboxylates act as bidentate (D). The one unit of the complex also possesses four disordered

Fig. 3. The coordination environment around Cu^{II} ions in the complex. Hydrogen atoms and cp ligands except for one carboxylate groups have been omitted for clarity.

Fig. 4. Infinite 3D supramolecular network of Cu^{II} complex constructed by secondary interactions, provide three types of cavities (C1, C2, C3).

water molecules (O1w, O2w, O3w and O4w) together with a methanol molecule. In our earlier report²², it has been shown that in case of Zn^{II} complex, the carboxylate groups of this ligand possess two different coordination modes. In one mode, two carboxylate groups act in unidentate mode (A) and two carboxylates act in chelating/bridging bidentate mode (B) whereas in other mode two carboxylate groups act in unidentate mode (A) and remaining two carboxylate act as bidentate (D). However, in case of Cd^{II} complex, tetracarboxylate groups of cyclophane molecule show another coordination mode in

which two carboxylate groups act as chelating bidentate mode (D) and two carboxylate groups act as chelating/bridging bidentate mode (B). This study supports the composition of the complex $[\{\text{Cu}(\text{2,2}'\text{-bpy})\}_2(\text{cp})].4\text{H}_2\text{O}.\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ as assigned by its elemental analysis. Secondary building units (SBUs) extend in a 3D supramolecular structure along crystallographic axis as depicted in Fig. 4. This framework provides three types of cavity marked as C1, C2 and C3, PLATON analysis of the crystals shows the presence of 13 non-conventional H-bonding interactions. In all interactions C-H acts as H-donor

whereas oxygen acts as H-acceptor atom.

Electron spin resonance :

The ESR spectrum of the powder of complex at liquid N₂ temperature shows typical four-lines pattern as expected from ⁶³Cu nucleus, it is depicted in Fig. 5. In this complex, three parallel hyperfine lines are well resolved giving $g_{\parallel} = 2.25$, $A_{\parallel} = 150$ Gauss, $g_{\perp} = 2.04$ and $g_0 = 2.11$. However, g_0 value is calculated using the rela-

tionships, $g_0 = (g_{\parallel} + 2g_{\perp})/3^{26}$.

Binding studies :

A solution of H₄cp (1×10^{-4} M in DMSO) is titrated by addition of 0.1 equivalent of hexafluorobenzene hfb in methanol at regular interval till no change in corresponding absorbance (λ , 269 nm) is observed at 1 : 1 composition (Fig. 6). The values of association constants using Benesi-Hilde Brand equation²⁷ was calculated and found

Fig. 5. ESR spectrum of Cu^{II} complex.

Fig. 6. Changes in the UV-Vis absorption spectra of H₄cp (100 μM) in DMSO solution with incremental addition of hexafluorobenzene (0–150 μM) in methanol.

$K_a = 2.6 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$. Subsequently emission titrations were also carried again by addition of 0.1 equivalent of hexafluorobenzene to cyclophane at regular interval. The emission peak at 379 nm emanated from corresponding solution is shown in Fig. 7. The decrease in the intensity is continued until addition of 1 : 1 composition is reached. The ^1H NMR titrations were also carried out by gradual addition of hexafluorobenzene to a fixed concentration of cyclophane ($1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$) and corresponding spectral features are shown in Fig. 8. A perusal of the spectral pattern clearly indicates that peaks observed for carboxylate group of H_4cp at δ 12.4 ppm shifted to δ 12.2 ppm after addition of 0.5 equivalent of hexafluorobenzene and finally shifted at δ 12.0 ppm on complete addition of 1.0 equivalent of hexafluorobenzene. However, to see the probability of binding of the cyclophane with hexafluorobenzene at higher molar ratio, the spectrum in corresponding molar ratio (1 : 2) was also recorded. But, it does not show any further change in peak position of carboxylate group of the cyclophane. Thus, ^1H NMR

Fig. 7. Changes in the luminescence of H_4cp ($100 \mu\text{M}$) in DMSO solution with incremental addition of hexafluorobenzene ($0\text{--}150 \mu\text{M}$) in methanol.

experiment supported the binding of H_4cp with hfb through its carboxylic groups. Since Cu^{II} complex was found insoluble in most of the common solvents, further studies using the complex could not be made.

Fig. 8. ^1H NMR spectral patterns observed upon addition of hexafluorobenzene with H_4cp [(a), free H_4cp ; (b), H_4cp + 0.5 eq. hexafluorobenzene; (c), H_4cp + 1.0 eq. hexafluorobenzene; (d), H_4cp + 1.5 eq. hexafluorobenzene; (e), H_4cp + 2.0 eq. hexafluorobenzene].

Photoluminescent property of Cu^{II} complex :

The photoluminescence of the complex is examined at room temperature and corresponding spectral feature are shown in Fig. 9. Upon excitation at $\lambda_{ex} = 310$ nm, dual emissions from the complex are observed at ~ 377 nm and ~ 470 nm. Since in solid state, free 2,2'-bpy group emits at $\lambda_{em} = 380$ nm owing to its $\pi - \pi^*$ transition²⁸, first emission peak from the complex is assigned to arise from its intra-ligand transition. However, lower energy emission observed at ~ 470 nm from the complex is considered to arise from a metal ligand charge-transfer transition in view of earlier report²⁹.

Fig. 9. Photoluminescence spectrum of complex in solid state at room temperature.

Thermogravimetric (TG) analysis of Cu^{II} complex :

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of the complex was performed under nitrogen atmosphere and is shown in Fig. 10. A weight loss of 7.2% between 40–100 °C is assigned to the loss of four co-crystallized water molecules along with the loss of a methanol molecule (calculated per formula unit weight loss = 7.2%). A second weight loss of 56.6% occurs between 260–491 °C. It may involve the loss of terminal 2,2'-bpy group and a part of cyclophane framework. However, final decomposition starts at 491 °C and continues up to 800 °C at which only 30% residue is remained.

Fig. 10. TGA pattern of the complex

Experimental

Materials and method :

A.R. grade reagents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and Merck, used without further purification. Elemental analysis was carried using a Carbo-Erba elemental analyzer 1108. IR spectra were recorded as KBr pellets on a Varian 3100 FT-IR spectrometer. TGA measurements were performed on a Perkin-Elmer Pyris diamond TG-DTA instrument at a heating rate of 10 °C/min in nitrogen atmosphere with flowing rate of 200 ml/min in the temperature range of 20–800 °C. The UV-Vis and luminescence spectra of solid complex was measured using Shimadzu UV-1700 and Hitachi F-4500 spectrofluorometer. However, titrations in solution were carried out using JASCO-V630 spectrophotometer and Perkin-Elmer LS45 spectrofluorometer respectively. The precursor, Cu(bpy)(NO₃)₂·H₂O was prepared using the procedure reported by Sen *et al.*³⁰.

X-Ray crystallographic studies :

The crystals of complex suitable for X-ray measurement are grown directly from their corresponding reaction mixtures in DMF/MeOH/H₂O (6 : 2 : 0.4 by volume) at room temperature and X-ray diffraction data are collected by mounting a single-crystal of the sample on glass fibers. Oxford diffraction XCALIBUR-EOS diffractometer is used for the determination of cell pa-

rameters and intensity data collection at room temperature. Appropriate empirical absorption corrections were applied using multi-scan programs. Monochromated Mo K_{α} radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) was used for the measurements. The crystal structures are solved by direct methods using SHELXS-97 program³¹ and are refined by full matrix least squares SHELXL-97³². Drawings were carried out using MERCURY³³, DIAMOND³⁴ and special computations carried out with PLATON³⁵.

Synthesis of cyclophane (H_4cp) :

Cyclophane H_4cp is synthesized using procedure reported earlier by Hayashida *et al.*¹⁷ and it is characterized by its IR, 1H NMR spectrum. IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3197(w), 2926(s), 1739(vs), 1644(vs), 1509(m), 1409(s), 1251(s), 1186(s), 794(w); 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 300 MHz, ppm) : δ 1.96 (8H, m), 2.04 (8H, m), 2.33 (8H, m), 3.48 (2H, m), 3.94 (4H, s), 7.051 (8H, d), 7.34 (8H, d) and 11.9 (4H, s).

Synthesis of $\{[Cu(2,2'-bpy)]_2(cp)\} \cdot 4H_2O \cdot CH_3OH$:

In the synthetic procedure, $Cu(2,2'-bipyridyl)(NO_3)_2 \cdot H_2O$ (0.361 g, 1 mmol) and H_4cp (0.452 g, 0.5 mmol) were taken together in DMF (6 ml), methanol (2 ml) and water (0.4 mL) containing four equivalent triethylamine. At room temperature, few solid were still remained which were then dissolved by addition of few drops of 5 N HNO_3 . The clear solution thus obtained was then heated at 120 °C for 6 h. It was cooled slowly to room temperature, giving tiny block shaped, green crystals after two weeks. Yield : ~66% (Found C, 59.19; H, 5.48; N, 7.55. Calcd. for $C_{71}H_{73}N_8O_{17}Cu_2$: C, 59.32; H, 5.12; N, 7.80%); UV-Vis (Solid state) : $\lambda_{max}(nm)$ 320, 450, 694; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3315(w), 3078(w), 2928(w), 1650(vs), 1601(s), 1580(vs), 1507(m), 1407(s), 1280(s), 1170(s), 730(w), 652(m), 532(m). Summary of crystallographic data for Cu^{II} complex; $M = 1437.45$, crystal system - Triclinic, space group - P-1, $a/\text{\AA} - 15.412$, $b/\text{\AA} - 16.085$, $c/\text{\AA} - 17.826$, α (°) - 65.60, β (°) - 81.14, $Z = 2$, $D_c/mg \text{ m}^{-3} - 1.336$, $R(int) - 0.0831$, index ranges $-19 \leq h \leq 19$, $-21 \leq k \leq 21$, $-22 \leq l \leq 23$, $wR_2 - 0.2555$, GoF- 1.120.

Conclusion :

The targeted cyclophane (H_4cp) interacts with hexafluorobenzene through its carboxylate groups. However, it forms an interesting polymeric complex with Cu^{II} -

2,2'-bipyridine under mild reaction condition. The lattice packing study of the complex provides three-dimensional supramolecular network having cavity. The carboxylate groups of cyclophane react with Cu^{II} -2,2'-bipyridine in a variety of coordination modes, different than those reported earlier with Zn^{II} - and Cd^{II} -2,2'-bipyridines.

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Appendix A

Supplementary material :

CCDC reference no. 821834 contains the supplementary crystallographic data for Cu^{II} complex. This data can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>, or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK, Fax (+44) 1223-336-033, or E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

References

1. F. Vogtle, C. Seel and P.-M. Windscheif, in "Comprehensive Supramolecular Chemistry", Pergamon, Oxford, 1996, 2, pp. 211-265.
2. A. C. Benniston, P. Gunning and R. D. Peacock, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2005, 70, 115.
3. J. Bobacka, V. Vaananen, A. Lewenstam and A. Ivaska, *Talanta*, 2004, 63, 135.
4. J. M. Coteron, C. Vicent, C. Bosso and S. Penades, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1993, 115, 10066.
5. E. Weber, in J. J. Kroschwitz (ed.), "Kirk-Othmer Encyclopedia of Chemical Technology", 4th ed., Suppl., Wiley, New York, 1998, 352.
6. A. R. Choudhary, R. G. Bhat, T. N. Guru Row and S. Chandrasekaran, *Cryst. Growth Des.*, 2007, 7, 844.
7. M. Mascal, A. Armstrong and M. D. Bartberger, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, 124, 6274.
8. A. P. Cote, A. I. Benin, N. W. Ockwig, M. O'Keeffe, A. J. Matzger and O. M. Yaghi, *Science*, 2005, 310, 1166.
9. O. M. Yaghi, M. O'Keeffe, N. W. Ockwig, H. K. Chae, M. Eddaoudi and J. Kim, *Nature*, 2003, 423, 705.
10. C. D. Wu, A. Hu, L. Zhang and W. B. Lin, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, 127, 8940.
11. Q. R. Fang, G. S. Zhu, M. Xue, Z. P. Wang, J. Y. Sun and S. L. Qiu, *Cryst. Growth Des.*, 2008, 83, 19.

12. K. Koh, A. G. Wong-Foy and A. J. Matzger, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2008, **47**, 677.
13. S. Kitagawa and M. Kondo, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1998, **71**, 1739.
14. A. J. Blake, N. R. Champness, P. Hubberstey, W. S. Li, M. A. Withersby and M. Schreoder, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1999, **183**, 117.
15. K. E. Holmes, P. F. Kelly and M. R. Elsegood, *Dalton Trans.*, 2004, 3488.
16. P. S. Wang, C. N. Moorefield, M. Panzer and G. R. Newkome, *Chem. Commun.*, 2005, 465.
17. H. F. Zhu, J. Fan, T.-a. Okamura, Z. H. Zhang, G. X. Liu, K. B. Yu, W. Y. Sun and N. Ueyama, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2006, **45**, 3941.
18. Z. H. Zhang, T.-a. Okamura, Y. Hasegawa, H. Kawaguchi, L. Y. Kong, W. Y. Sun and N. Ueyama, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2005, **44**, 6219.
19. S. S. Y. Chui, S. M. F. Lo, J. P. H. Charmant, A. G. Orpen and I. D. Williams, *Science*, 1999, **283**, 1148.
20. Z. H. Zhang, Y. Song, T.-a. Okamura, Y. Hasegawa, W. Y. Sun and N. Ueyama, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2006, **45**, 2896.
21. R. Q. Zou, H. Sakurai and Q. Xu, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2006, **45**, 2542.
22. N. Kumari, R. Prajapati, O. Hayashida and L. Mishra, *Polyhedron*, 2010, **29**, 2755.
23. H.-P. Jia, W. Li, Z.-F. Ju and J. Zhang, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2006, **21**, 4264.
24. O. Hayashida and I. Hamachi, *J. Incl. Phenom. Macro. Chem.*, 2005, **53**, 57.
25. S. Roy, T. N. Mandal, A. K. Barik, S. Gupta, M. S. E. Fallah, J. Terceiro, R. J. Butcher and S. K. Kar, *Dalton Trans.*, 2009, 8215.
26. H. Yokoi and A. W. Addison, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, **16**, 1341.
27. S. Bhattacharya, S. K. Nayak, S. K. Chattopadhyay, M. Banerjee and A. K. Mukherjee, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 2001, **57**, 309.
28. R.-X. Yuan, R.-G. Xiong, Y.-L. Xie, X. Z. You, S.-M. Peng and G.-H. Lee, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.*, 2001, **4**, 384.
29. J. Tao, J.-X. Shi, M.-L. Tong, X.-X. Zhang and X.-M. Chen, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2001, **40**, 6328.
30. S. Sen, S. Mitra, P. Kundu, M. K. Saha, C. Kruga and J. Bruckmann, *Polyhedron*, 1997, **16**, 2475.
31. G. M. Sheldrick, SHELXS-97 Program for the Solution of Crystal Structures, University of Göttingen, Göttingen, Germany, 1997.
32. G. M. Sheldrick, *Acta Cryst. (A)*, 1990, **46**, 467.
33. MERCURY, New software for searching the Cambridge structural database and visualizing crystal structures, I. J. Bruno, J. C. Cole, P. R. Edgington, M. K. Kessler, C. F. Macrae, P. McCabe, J. Pearson and R. Taylor, *Acta Cryst. (B)*, 2002, **58**, 389.
34. K. Brandenburg and H. Putz, DIAMOND Version 3.0, Crystal Impact, GbR, Postfach 1251, D-53002 Bonn Germany, 2004.
35. PLATON, A. L. Spek, *J. Appl. Cryst.*, 2003, **3**, 67.

